

DEVELOP CREATIVITY IN STUDENTS OPPORTUNITIES FOR INNOVATION

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ANNOTATION

This article talks about innovative opportunities for the development of creative abilities of students. The main purpose of this article is to develop the skills and abilities of students to develop their independent work, to work with sources that can provide broad and in-depth information on a wide range of topics, and on this basis to draw lessons from the literature. essential for creative development.

INTRODUCTION

Their discoveries are invaluable in the development of mankind. If we look at the life path of the great geniuses, we can be sure that they were able to create something new in science, art or religious teaching while leaving a mark in history. Geniuses such as Abu Ali ibn Sina, Al Khorazmi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Imam Al Bukhari Abdullah Awlani, who contributed to the development of humanity and science, created innovations in the ways of life and their directions, were creative. have been

Humanity's desire for innovation and development is expressed by historical evolutionary development. Because creativity is the basis of every creative activity. So, creativity, creativity has existed since ancient times, only the creative process, creativity, that is, the concept of creativity and scientific research on the concept of creativity began in the last century.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. Relying on the rich heritage of our ancestors mentioned above, the presence of creative ability in personal behavior and activities is determined by the ability to make independent decisions on the

basis of a new approach to the problem, using a non-standard solution, unlike the usual situations and experiences . In fact, everyone may have an innate ability to be creative. According to Maslow, creativity is unique to every human being, it is innate, it develops as a result of education and training in the social environment, or on the contrary, it disappears. We believe that there are several factors that make creativity impossible. The content of education and the social environment are the leading factors in the emergence and development of creativity.

Foreign scientists such as N. Marsh, F. Vernoy, S. Burt attributed the possibilities of developing creativity in students to previous life experience, knowledge and skills, and the environment.

Creativity about scientific research a foreigner who took scholars F. Heddon and G. Littons creativity development opportunities in society culture , tradition and of values to himself feature with represents _

Albert Einstein about curiosity, which is a part of creativity " In fact, it is almost a miracle that modern educational methods have not completely stifled sacred curiosity, because, in addition to stimulating curiosity, it requires freedom above all, otherwise, it will be formless and destroyed .

Students will have the ability to develop their creativity, prepare for independent work in the current globalization era, and create a healthy competitive environment in their future professional activities. The use of innovative tools in the development of creativity allows students to acquire modern methods and apply them in practice in their future activities, in the educational process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS. In the current era of globalization requires the creation of new forms, tools and methods of the educational process for the development of the creative activity of students: the content and structure of the educational subject; control of students' acquisition of knowledge, skills, and abilities; implementation of critical thinking in the educational process; organizational issues; modern classification of educational principles; determines

that the development of student creativity is carried out in many stages.

Innovative approaches are invisible in terms of the development of students' creativity as an organizer of their general culture, as a pedagogical structure of opportunities for the development of individual creativity as a method of self-formation, and as a combination of his inner world during the mastery of the entire scope of his competencies . Based on the points you mentioned based on an innovative approach, a structure for developing students' creative abilities was developed.

Although the term "creative competence" was first used by the American scientist P. Ch. Joseph, R. Epstein began to use it as a scientific concept in science since the 80s of the last century. According to R. Epstein, "Creative competence" is the ability to adapt and apply acquired knowledge, to independently complete the sequence of knowledge and to improve oneself.

Competence is a set of personal experience of students in performing any activity. The formation of a creative competent structure in students is the modern laws, content, principles, forms, methods, tools of education in the process of teaching specialized subjects, as well as the educational process in the spiritual and professional development of the student and the special measures aimed at its implementation. is a preparatory activity.

D. Bogoyavlenskaya pays special attention to the competence that reduces or develops creativity in the process of studying creativity. His according to success competence creativity invisible to be hindrance to do possible determined .

G. Smolyaninova considers the types of modern multimedia tools and the skills of working with electronic tools in the formation of students' competence.

In recent years, much emphasis has been placed on creativity in scientific activities. In this process, the scope of using innovative tools is becoming more and more active. First of all, this requires an integrated approach to education, pedagogical innovation, effective use of modern methods and ICT tools.

CONCLUSION . According to the state standard of higher education, in the subject "Technology of Teaching Methodological Sciences", students' creative activity, creative competence, development of mental intelligence, speech culture, knowledge, skills, competences in mastering the technologies and methods of teaching specialized subjects serves to form the ability to apply in future activities. By teaching this subject, great emphasis is placed on developing students' thinking, preparing projects and putting them into practice, demonstrating their creativity, and developing their acquired educational skills.

Creative competencies are realized when a solution to a common problem is found in a new, non-standard way, when a new idea is created, the essence of which is innovation . Creative competence, innovative form , method and development of tools , opportunities to use them in different situations. It is directed to a certain goal and formed within certain criteria. It is aimed at the development of the field in which innovation is applied, and it requires encouraging its participants to look at the current situation with a new perspective. Based on an innovative approach, it is necessary to form students' self-awareness, the ability to feel the breadth of the world of thought and imagination, and motivation in the universal cultural and spiritual values as opportunities to develop students' creativity.

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